

TELECOMMUNICATIONS REGULATION IN SERBIA

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I INTRODUCTION

What would be the life of modern man without any telecommunications as we know them today? Would contemporary humanity be denied something important, without which it cannot be, or people would live much more slowly, calmer and better? We can get different answers to these questions, but one thing is certain that whatever opinion people have about it, the largest part of the human population is the direct user of telecommunications. Many of them are directly involved in the telecommunications business or their business largely depends on telecommunications.

Today's telecommunications as an extremely important economic activity in each country, or if we want a global activity³, generate significant economic growth in each country. As an activity of such importance, it is inevitably legally regulated either at the international or national level. Today's development of telecommunications, in the technical-technological sense, also requires appropriate legal regulations. In this sense, there is an attempt to unify as many international regulations as possible in this area. Even countries that do not belong to the most developed in terms of telecommunications, try to follow the world trends and the pace set by the most developed countries in this domain.

The Republic of Serbia does not differ too much on this issue from other countries. By developing global telecommunications it also had to comply with its telecommunications regulations, accepting the fact that the field of telecommunications is of paramount importance to the national economy. It led this trip from a strictly state-controlled business, which practically had the status of monopoly, to today's focus on the existence of the private sector in telecommunications and the development of competitiveness. The great expansion that the telecommunications business has experienced by creating new regulations related to this area inevitably led to changes in the emergence of new regulatory bodies (agencies), with the main goal of proposing/create regulations and supervision

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³ According to STATISTA, the value of telecommunications for 2016 is 1.129 mil.€ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/268636/telecommunications-services-revenue-since-2005-by-region/>

in telecommunications operations. Since the Republic of Serbia has the status of a candidate⁴ for a member in the European Union (EU), regulations are regularly aligned with the regulations coming from the EU. Serbia uses in various ways the help of EU institutions, as well as the practice of EU countries in order to apply its telecommunication regulations in practice in the most efficient manner. In this way, it is a possibility for the state of Serbia to regulate the telecommunications sector in a transparent way, protecting the rights of the users and the rights of entrepreneurs and companies as providers of telecommunications services.

Currently market of telecommunications in Serbia revenues is around 1.5 billion euros a year, which makes up around 4.5% of GDP. Structurally, most of these revenues are still related to mobile telephony, so investments⁵ in the field of telecommunications amount to 262.5 mil. euro (data from 2016) for the most part related to this segment. In order to maintain the existing and further development of the market in the field of telecommunications, it will be extremely important to be openness, competitiveness, impartiality as well as a modern legal framework.

II REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

In principle, the activities in the field of telecommunications in Serbia are regulated by law and by-laws. In accordance with the constitutional provisions where the affairs of the state administration are performed by ministries and other administrative bodies determined by law, the competent body of the state administration in the field of telecommunications is currently in Serbia, the Ministry of Trade, Tourism and Telecommunications. On the proposal of the ministry responsible for telecommunications and information society, the Government of the R. of Serbia determines the policy in the field of electronic communications and adopts strategic acts and action plans for their implementation which determines the principles, goals and priorities of electronic communications development.

Telecommunications tasks performed by the competent ministry relate primarily to electronic communications and postal traffic, regulation and security in the field of electronic communications and postal traffic, inspection, supervision, as well as other segments of telecommunications, as determined by law. Likewise, on the basis of constitutional powers (Article 137, paragraph 3 of the Constitution of the Republic of Serbia), public authorities may also be entrusted with the law by special bodies through which a regulatory function is exercised in certain areas or activities.

⁴Serbia has become 01.03.2012. a candidate for membership in the European Union and has so far opened 12 negotiating chapters

⁵According to the available data from RATEL amount of investments for 2016 is 262.5 mil. euro

This regulatory function is performed by an independent regulatory body as an independent organization, the Regulatory Agency for Electronic Communications and Postal Services-RATEL⁶ (hereinafter: the Agency), which is in compliance with the Law on Electronic Communications (Official Gazette of RS, No. 44/10). The law is compliant with the 2002 EU regulatory framework and regulates the legal position of the Agency where Article 7 (1) states that the Agency's objective is to:

- effectively implement the established policy in the field of electronic communications;
- encourage competition of electronic communications networks and services, improving their capacity and quality;
- contribute to the development of the electronic communications market and protect the interests of users of electronic communications.

In its work, the Agency is functionally and financially independent from state authorities, as well as from organizations and persons engaged in the electronic communications activities, which is in accordance with the regulations on public agencies in Serbia. Supervision in the work of the Agency is performed by the competent Ministry of Trade, Tourism and Telecommunications. Article 8 of the Law on Electronic Communications stipulates that the Agency, within its legal competence:

- 1) pass bylaws;
- 2) decide on the rights and obligations of operators and users;
- 3) Cooperate with bodies and organizations competent in the field of broadcasting, competition protection, consumer protection, personal data protection and other bodies and organizations on issues relevant to the field of electronic communications;
- 4) Cooperate with the competent regulatory and professional bodies of the member states of the European Union and other countries in order to harmonize the practice of applying regulations in the field of electronic communications and encouraging the development of cross-border electronic communications networks and services;
- 5) participate in the work of international organizations and institutions in the field of electronic communications as a national regulatory body in the field of electronic communications;

⁶The Republic Agency for Electronic Communications and Postal Services or RATEL is established by the Law on Telecommunications (2003), and started its work on 19.12.2005.

- 5a) performs regulatory and other tasks in the field of postal services, in accordance with a special law regulating postal services;
- 6) perform other tasks in accordance with the law.

The Agency performs the duties referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article as entrusted tasks, impartially and publicly.

One of the key changes in the work of this regulatory agency happened in 2010 when the previous Telecommunications Law was changed⁷ and the entry into force of the Electronic communications law⁸ RATEL has become the Republic Agency for Electronic Communications and Postal Services⁹.

i. **Relevant national regulation in telecommunications Laws**

- Electronic Communications Law¹⁰;
- Law on Amendments and Supplements to the Electronic Communications Law¹¹;
- Law on Information Security¹²;
- Law on Amendments to the Law on Information Security¹³;
- Law on Amendments to the Law on Postal Services¹⁴;
- Law on Electronic Document Act, Electronic Identification and Trusted Services in Electronic Business¹⁵;
- Law on Protection against Non-Ionizing Radiation¹⁶.

Bylaws

Bylaws in the field of telecommunications may be issued by the competent ministry or the Agency in accordance with the authority they possess. Some of the most important bylaws:

⁷ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 44/03, 36/06 and 50/09

⁸ Official Gazette, No. 44/10

⁹ The Constitutional Court decided in Decision IVz-128/2012 of 24.04.2014. explained the status of RATEL as an independent regulatory body

¹⁰ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia No. 44/10

¹¹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 62/14

¹² Official Gazette of RS No. 6/16

¹³ Official Gazette of RS No. 94/17

¹⁴ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 62/14

¹⁵ Official Gazette Republic of Serbia, No. 94/17 of 19 October 2017

¹⁶ Official Gazette of RS, No. 36/09

- Rulebook on Authorization for Measuring and Testing¹⁷;
- Rulebook on Radio Equipment and Telecommunications Terminal Equipment¹⁸;
- Rulebook on universal service¹⁹;
- Rulebook on Radio Corridors²⁰;
- Rulebook on the method of using radio frequencies under the general authorization regime²¹;
- Decree on determining the plan for the purpose of radio frequency bands²²;
- Rulebook on requirements in terms of staff, equipment and premises of an undertaking, company or other legal entity authorized for measuring and testing the operation of electronic communications networks and services, associated facilities, electronic communications, equipment and terminal equipment²³;
- Rulebook on the technical and other requirements when building associated infrastructure necessary for installing electronic communications networks, associated facilities when constructing and commercial and residential buildings²⁴;
- Rulebook on the content and method of application of the international agreement on interconnection²⁵;
- Rulebook on number portability for services provided through public mobile communications networks²⁶.

III TELECOMMUNICATIONS AND INTERNET

i. RADIO COMMUNICATIONS AND USE OF SPECTRUM

The field of radio communications, except Electronic Communications Law, is additionally regulated by a number of bylaws that regulate the use of the radio-frequency spectrum in a more detailed way. In order for the radio communications to function properly, it is extremely important to use the radio frequency spectrum.

¹⁷ Official Gazette of RS, No. 44/10

¹⁸ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 11/12

¹⁹ Official Gazette of RS, No. 24/12

²⁰ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 44/10

²¹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 28/13

²² Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 44/10

²³ Official Gazette of RS, no. 13/12

²⁴ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 123/10

²⁵ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia No. 104/14

²⁶ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia No. 101/14

The management of radio frequency spectrum is regulated by Article 81 of Electronic Communications Law based on the principles of rationality, economy, publicity and non-discrimination. As a limited resource, in order to be used appropriately, radio frequencies are managed on the basis of the radio frequency band's purpose plan, which must be in compliance with:

- national interests;
- international agreements; and
- User interest.

The purpose of the plan is to be adopted by the Government on the proposal of the ministry, which is prepared by the Agency. The frequency allocation plan operates according to the same principle.

Within the competence of the regulatory body are the tasks of issuing an individual license for the use of radio frequencies and the control of the radiofrequency spectrum. The issue of licenses also applies to radio frequency users, that is, radio stations that are on board or aircraft. An individual license shall be issued in accordance with the public bidding procedure where, due to the limited availability of radio frequencies, such a procedure must be carried out. Agency's duty is to carry out such a procedure transparently. The validity of an individual license cannot be longer than 10 years and this right cannot be given, rented or otherwise transferred to another person.

For the purposes of market or technical testing of products and services or other necessities, it is possible to obtain a temporary permit, which cannot be longer than 60 days. In the event of improper work, the user may be revoked. In addition to the individual license regimes, the regulatory body in case of a negligible risk of interference, or in the case of harmonized radio frequency bands, may allow the use of radio frequencies under the general authorization regime. Defense and Security Bodies as well as Special Services use specific purpose radio frequencies in accordance with the plan of purpose and are obliged to notify the Agency in advance of their initiation of the use of radio frequencies.

In Serbia, continuous control²⁷ of the use of radio frequency spectrum is performed and these tasks are performed by the Agency. In the case of control of the radio frequency spectrum intended for the distribution and broadcasting of media content, the Agency shall, in cooperation with the authority competent for

²⁷In 2016, RATEL conducted more than 7,000 measurements from its control and measuring centers and mobile transmission stations

broadcasting on the use of the radio spectrum shall be kept in a database the Agency.

In terms of coordinated and rational use of radio frequencies, the regulatory body cooperates with the regulatory agencies of other countries both for narrowband systems and for broadband systems. Most often for terrestrial systems in the range of 790-862 MHz or GSM coordination in the range 1710-1785 / 1805-1880 MHz. Cooperation with the ITU on various activities related to the field of radio communications is also an important segment of the work on inter-cooperation cooperation on this issue. Thus, the competent ministry prepared the draft Law on the confirmation of the final acts of the World Radio Communication Conference²⁸ respectively, obtaining the possibility that these acts could be applied in the R. of Serbia. This would further correlate the use of the channel between neighboring countries and further prevent the possibility of disturbance in border areas.

ii. Access to the installation of telecommunication infrastructure

Installation of telecommunication infrastructure in practice can often cause problems in a reality. These problems are most often solved by determining the public interest for the expropriation of real estate, in accordance with the law governing the expropriation or a right of easement. Both methods are legally regulated (Articles 49 and 50 Electronic Communications Law).

Since the operator has the right to request the exercise of the aforementioned right with the aim of installing the telecommunications structure, if it is a private property, it is necessary to conclude an agreement that will further regulate the mutual rights with regard to the right to serve, as well as the amount of compensation for the use of that right. In the event that an agreement on the right to serve is not reached, it will be regulated by law. Above the real estate which is in public ownership by the competent authority will decide at the conclusion of the contract in a non-discriminatory manner within 30 days from the filing of the request for conclusion of the contract.

An operator may exercise the right, even if it is a joint use (including device collocation) for elements of the network when the right of easement or expropriation has been established before the other operator in order to use the capacities economically, efficiently and competitively or when the construction of new capacities would not it was possible on several grounds: security, cultural property, ecology.

²⁸ WRC-15 World Radio communication Conference (WRC) held in Geneva, Switzerland, 2-27 November 2015 is organized by ITU to review, and, as necessary, revise the Radio Regulations, the international treaty governing the use of the radio-frequency spectrum and the geostationary-satellite and non-geostationary-satellite orbits

Unless an agreement is reached with other operators for joint use within 60 days, the Agency will, ex officio, when the conditions are met, adopts a decision establishing the joint use.

For the purpose of rationality and better utilization of the capacities of telecommunication installations, the Agency is obliged to keep a database of the type of availability and the geographic location of the capacities, especially when it comes to the directions and capacities of telecommunication networks.

iii. Broadband networks

The regulatory framework relevant to the development of broadband networks and services in the Republic of Serbia besides Electronic Communications Law is composed of the following regulations:

- Law on the confirmation of the Final Acts of the Regional Conference on Radio Communications for the planning of digital terrestrial broadcasting services in parts of Region 1 and 3, in the frequency bands 174-230 MHz and 470-862 MHz (RRC 06)²⁹;
- The Law on the Confirmation of the Protocol on Amendments and Supplements to Certain Parts of the Regional Agreement for the European Broadcasting Zone (Stockholm, 1961) with Resolutions (RRC-06- Rev. ST61)³⁰;
- Law on the Confirmation of Final Acts of the World Conference on Radio Communications (WRC-07)³¹;
- Regulation Stipulating Radio Frequency Bands Allocation Plan³².

The right of an operator to provide services to users is to establish interconnection with another operator, access to network elements and associated assets of the other operator in the manner prescribed by law. If it exists on the market, significant market power (hereinafter: SMP) is obliged to offer other operators interconnection. When interconnection occurs, operators are obliged to report this to the agency. In the case of special needs of the defense and security authorities as well as emergency services, the agency may oblige the operator to prioritize interconnection.

A recent analysis of the wholesale call termination market in the public telephone network has shown that there are as many as 35 SMP operators³³ in Serbia. With

²⁹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia - International Treaties, number 4/10

³⁰ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia - International Agreements, No. 1/10

³¹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia - International Agreements", No. 2/11

³² Official Gazette of RS, no. 99/12

³³ Source: telekomunikacije.net

this analysis, Agency practically found that all registered fixed telephony operators fall under the dominant category - the SMP in the specific market.

Recognizing the importance of electronic communications development, the Government of R. of Serbia, within the framework of the Development Strategy for the next generation networks, by 2023, set the goals and tasks to be achieved. Broadband access to users who primarily relies on telephone, internet and digital TVs has been raised to a new level. This new level implies services from administration, education, health, trade and banking. This would raise the overall level of competitiveness of the state to a new higher standard. In view of the proclaimed goal of Serbia's entry into the EU, the activities in this sphere should, by using new technologies, be able to connect with a single European digital market³⁴.

Obviously there is a lot of work to be done on this issue because the data indicate that R. of Serbia is lagging behind in relation to the EU countries and in the use of the Internet³⁵ and that when broadband access is at a level of 57.5% versus 76%. The situation is even worse when looking at the coverage of networks for accessing a new generation. The data is only about 30% of users compared to the EU, where it is 71%.

Achieving broadband access enhancement goals will not be possible without changes in the infrastructure of the entire network that exists in the RS. Therefore, the Government of R. of Serbia adopted an Action Plan for the Efficient Use of Telecommunication Infrastructure ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia" No. 36/2017) which will enable the improvement of the telecommunication network capacity to be used more efficiently. This would create conditions for the unified national broadband network to be further upgraded. The Agency as a regulatory body maintains a database on the capacities of telecommunication infrastructure pursuant to the Regulation on the manner of collecting and publishing data on the type, availability and geographical location of the electronic communications network capacity³⁶ which is in accordance with the Directive³⁷.

iv. Universal service

Universal Service is legally listed and must be provided on a neutral basis in order to satisfy quality at affordable prices. The competent ministry is in charge of

³⁴Digital Single Market Strategy for Europe (CELEX 52015DC0192)

³⁵61.85% of citizens regularly use the internet, compared to the EU average of 76%

³⁶ Official Gazette of RS, No. 66/15

³⁷Directive 2002/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7th March 2002 on a common regulatory framework for electronic communications networks and services (Framework Directive) CELEX 32002L0021

the scope, geographical coverage and quality of the provision of public services, but it does soon a proposal along with an analysis of the agency.

The Agency for the purpose of universal service provision may designate one or more operators in an objective and non-discriminatory manner. The operation of the universal service operator, its operation and the quality of the services of the agency, is controlled at least once every three years. During the provision of universal service, an operator may face excessive costs that must be documented to the regulatory body. In order to over compensate the overcompensation of the operator, the funds that operators pay for the name of the universal service are provided. Funds are placed in a special account held by the Agency.

v. Numbering

Allocation of numbers and identification of networks is under the authority of the Agency in accordance with the numbering plan, which must be published on the Agency website. In order to be eligible for the numbering, the operator must have a license to use the numbering obtained by a decision issued by the Agency. The solution as such must contain relevant information about the applicant for the use of the numbering. License to use the numbering is issued for a period that cannot exceed 10 years. Extension of the license may only be made under the same conditions as for obtaining a new license.

Mobile telephony users in the R. of Serbia can transfer³⁸ their numbers from one network provider to another. By this way, providers are obliged to enable subscribers to keep a number from a numbering plan at a specific location to which the geographic access code refers. Such a subscriber's request to the operator is considered a request for termination of the subscription contract. The moment when the number of subscribers is disconnected from the operator's network, the contract is deemed to be terminated.

vi. Internet regulation

Internet in RS is regulated through telecommunication regulations however; the content transmitted over the Internet is subject to regulation of media regulations that include the Law on Advertising and the Law on e-commerce³⁹. In this way, the infrastructure and the content of the transfer are separated, which makes it possible for the ISP to be responsible for the content transmitted over the Internet. However, as these regulations require ISPs are obliged to apply technical measures

³⁸ Starting from 01.07.2011. mobile users are allowed to transfer their user number to another operator

³⁹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 41/2009 and 95/2013

to protect the network and thereby prevent its abuse, although they are not initially obliged to block any content or certain websites.

By interacting with the Internet, users can exchange various content and data, and it is possible that there will be abuse during such activities. The responsibility of the internet service provider (ISP) is excluded in this sense and the beneficiaries, if their right is violated by this way, can appeal to the court. Based on a court decision on this issue, the ISP must provide assistance to the user.

Since telecommunication networks are carrying out various types of communication by content and the volume of data transmitted by operators, they have the ability to otherwise charge the services provided or possibly block certain transmission. The legal provisions regulate this in a general manner in order to have a kind of "network neutrality". The Internet has long been able to communicate directly to users as it was previously reserved for different forms of telephony. With the advent of VoIP this has changed. Unlike the time 15 years ago when the major provider of Telekom Srbija was running a dispute⁴⁰ against some operators who then introduced VoIP because at that time there were no appropriate regulations today does not exist for certain regulations and is under the general authorization regime. The legal obligation of an operator planning to start VoIP activities is to notify the Agency in advance of this or eventual changes or the completion of these activities in advance.

IV. Market and price control

i. Market analysis, ownership and competitiveness

The issue of ownership and restrictions on the access to the telecommunications market in Serbia⁴¹ has passed its development path from the regulations that restricted this to the liberalization of the market. The current situation is that there are no restrictions on foreign ownership or foreign investments in the field of telecommunications. Except for the largest company on the R. of Serbia market in telecommunications MTS⁴², it can be seen that all other large companies belong to foreign owners.

⁴⁰In June 2002, Telekom Srbija filed a lawsuit against several VoIP providers: Absolut OK, Tech, NET ncs, BITS net, Visnet and Infosky

⁴¹The Serbian telecommunication services market is an oligopolistic type operated by three large systems: Telenor, MTS Telekom and VIP Mobile. <http://www.makroekonomija.org/0-dragovan-milicevic/vrednovanje-kompanije-telenor/>

⁴² MTS - Mobile Telephony of Serbia (marketed as mts since 2015 and formerly as mt:s from 1997 to 2015) is a consumer brand of Telekom Srbija under which it offers and provides all of its services to both private and corporate users

The duty of analyzing the telecommunications market based on the provisions of the Electronic Communications Law has the Agency as a regulatory body. In accordance with the delegated authority, the control of certain segments of the market is carried out, which determines the degree of competitiveness. The Electronic Communications Law prescribes that market analysis actions must be done at least once every three years in the case of relevant markets or additional analysis of other markets. The process of analyzing or determining the SMP must be carried out according to the EU recommendation. In cases where it is found that the competitiveness on the market is not appropriate, the Agency is determined by an operator or group that has a SMP. The Agency is not solely a regulatory body that regulates the telecommunications market in Serbia. In its regulatory actions, it works closely with the Commission for the Protection of Competition. It could be said that their work complement each other because the Agency is acting *ex ante* more while the Competition Commission does this *ex post*. For such activity, they have administrative powers and it is possible to review their decisions in court.

When it comes to fixed telecommunication network, Telekom Srbija still has SMP and its services in accordance with the rules must be provided under certain conditions, thereby depriving him of the possibility of collecting high retail prices. Prices for using mobile roaming services have been a problem for many years in terms of customer billing. Very often this has been exactly the subject of court disputes with operators due to the amount of bills. After the EU roaming on its territory as of 01.06.2017 on the basis of the Agreement on lowering the prices of roaming services in public mobile communication networks of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia and Serbia, signed on 29.09.2014. a dynamic was established that would lead through three phases of the roaming price to the level that exists as such in the EU. The last phase is currently underway and it is expected that the decision on the abolition of roaming for the countries signatories of the aforementioned agreement is expected these days.

Based on the Electronic communication Act⁴³, an analysis related to broadband Internet access is also carried out. In Serbia, as in many other countries, the Internet analysis is based on several bases regarding the number of users, then e-Commerce and e-Government services. Based on the BCG index⁴⁴, Serbia had a value of 70 which indicates an underdevelopment of business on the Internet compared to developed countries with indexes of over 100. For 2017, the Internet connection

⁴³ Art. 60, ¶ 1

⁴⁴ Boston Consulting Group index- one of the most prestigious management consulting firms in the world

has 68% of the households⁴⁵. This represents an increase of 3.3% in relation to 2016. Very important data for the development of the Internet in Serbia is that 61.9% of households have broadband internet connection, which is an increase of 4.1% compared to 2016, and 5.9% compared to 2015. Growth indicators are also shown in the number of computer users, which is by 1.1% more.

This data should also include the use of mobile phones where almost 5 million people use a mobile phone. Regarding the use of public administration, 32% of the internet population uses the opportunity to realize their administrative needs through internet communication. 1.270.000 people use public administration services. E-commerce services are also on the rise since 2017 compared to the previous year, this increase was 8.8%. Over 1.630.000 people bought or ordered goods via the Internet. Data on the use of cloud services are not yet impressive since only 19.5% of the internet population uses this feature. All previous data indicate that there is still plenty of room for improvement in the telecommunications market.

ii. Protection of users

The Regulatory Body is in charge of providing permanent protection for electronic communications users by acting on the user's complaints. By analyzing these complaints, it proposes certain solutions, but the Agency does not have the authority to conduct administrative proceedings. The Agency has the ability to conduct a peaceful resolution of the dispute outside the court so that the operator and the dissatisfied user lead to a satisfactory solution. In the event that the party does not come, the parties must contact the competent court. It should be noted that the most common cases of user complaints are based on the amount of account for used services, especially if it happens in roaming. Through conducting analyzes of complaints received by Agency's users, in the past years, has sent recommendations and orders to operators in order to harmonize their operations with the applicable regulations.

The Agency itself has also led active litigation in recent years. In general, they were administrative disputes and in some cases, commercial disputes. Administrative disputes were primarily related to lawsuits in which operators as license holders were dissatisfied with certain legal solutions and related to the establishment of fees.

V. CONCLUSION

Considering the strategic path that the R. of Serbia is moving towards, which is a full-fledged EU membership, the regulation of the field of telecommunications

⁴⁵ Data of the Republic Statistical Office R. of Serbia

is on the way to be harmonized with other EU member states. To accomplish this, there is still a lot of work to be done, but much depends on the pace of development of the telecommunications market. What can primarily be expected is that the development of the relevant market will lead to raising the competitiveness and level of service standards that will be available to the users. For this reason, the competent ministry will submit a draft of the new Electronic Communications Law⁴⁶, which will result in a new alignment with the EU telecommunication regulations. In this way, a legal framework will be created for a better business environment for operator protection, as well as user satisfaction. In the light of the implementation of these activities, the Agency will continue to work on further harmonization of secondary legislation. In order to comply with the EU, international agreements with neighboring countries were signed to a greater extent in order to better coordinate the use of limited radio frequency resources. ITU standards are also adopted.

Market analysis and price control remains one of the priorities of the regulatory body. At the beginning of 2017, there was also a price scam test when it comes in a package of services. The prices of roaming services as a frequent subject of dispute and dissatisfaction between operators and users on the road are that after the Phase III of the Agreement on reducing the prices of roaming services on public mobile communications networks between the ministries competent in the field of electronic communications: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, FYROM and the Republic of Serbia from 29.09.2014. It will be equal in the same way as in the EU countries⁴⁷. Market indicators themselves say that there will be many things in the future to be addressed: broadband, prices, infrastructure, e-administration, e-business, e-education. All this together provides room for even greater progress.

⁴⁶ In accordance with the document "NATIONAL PROGRAM FOR THE ADOPTION OF LEGAL PROVISIONS OF THE EUROPEAN UNION" - third revision

⁴⁷ At the summit of the EU and countries of the Western Balkans held in Sofia, Bulgaria, on 17.05.2018. officials announced that the process of market liberalization and the equalization of roaming prices in the EU countries will take about a year